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ROLE OF INVESTMENT & INFRASTRUCTURE IN DEVELOPMENT OF A STATE AND INFRASTRUCTURAL SCENARIO IN HARYANA

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ABSTRACT

Infrastructure plays paramount role in development of every state economy. When we look around the world, we found that Developed countries are head of developing and other backward states because of developed infrastructure facilities only. Every industrialist wants to investment of capital in such a state where infrastructure facilities are highly developed. Like continent America, Europe, Australia states government developed infrastructure facilities for industrialist and economic growth. It is true that development of infrastructure facilities attract capital investment from within country and outside of country in form FDI. Inflow of capital investment creates more jobs and taxes to government and rise level of quality of life. In India, states like Gujrat, Tamilnadu, Maharastra are head of others state because of infrastructure facilities and government of these states give importance to development of roads, water availability, power, railways, bridge, internet connectivity and many more.

Hence, this research study undertakes and tries to study the role of investment & infrastructure in development of a state and infrastructural scenario in Haryana. Data used in this study totally secondary in nature and gather from different website and other published articles in journals and newspapers.

KEY WORDS: *Investment, Infrastructure development, Haryana*

INTRODUCTION

Infrastructure plays paramount role in development of every state economy. When we look around the world, we found that Developed countries are head of developing and other backward states because of developed infrastructure facilities only. Every industrialist want to investment of capital in such a state where infrastructure facilities are exist. Like continent America, Europe, Australia states government developed infrastructure facilities for industrialist and economic growth. It is true that development of infrastructure facilities attract capital investment from within country and outside of country in form FDI. Inflow of capital investment creates more jobs and taxes to government and rise level of quality of life.

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Table 1: Industrial investments proposal in Haryana vis-à-vis India

Year	Haryana	India	Share of Haryana in India's total investment proposals
2009	2423	1040259	0.23
2010	10436	1736322	0.60
2011	8700	1539728	0.57
2012	5894	567868	1.04
2013	4172	530086	0.79
2014	2681	405027	0.66
2015(Feb)	366	75509	0.48

Source: PHD Research Bureau, Haryana: State Profile

Table 1 show the investment pattern in India and Haryana. It is inferred from the above table total investment in India in 2009 was Rs.1040259 crore and Haryana share 0.23% of total investment. Table shows the fluctuation in share of Haryana out of India's total investment.

Figure 1: Share of Haryana in India's total investment proposals

Figure 1 show the investment trend in Haryana. It is inferred from above figure that investment in Haryana is increasing from the year 2009 to 2012. Investment in Haryana was

highest in year 2012. It also inferred that after the year 2012 investment in Haryana decreasing constantly.

Table 2: Gross State Domestic Product and its Composition in Haryana

Components	FY 2008	FY 2011	FY 2014
GSDP at Current price (Rs. Crore)	151596	260621	388917
NSDP at Current price (Rs. Crore)	136584	237163	353714
Economic Growth % at Constant price	8.5	7.4	6.9
Sectoral Contribution in GSDP at current price (%)			
Agriculture	23	21	20
Industry	30	29	27
Services	47	50	53

Source: PHD Research Bureau, Haryana: State Profile

MAJOR INITIATIVE FOR INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENTS IN HARYANA

Railway & Metro

Railway is need of country as well as industry. Railway provides affordable transportation to industry for supply of raw material as finished goods. Union government announced and sanctioned Rewari-Jhajjar-Rohtak railway line in the railway budget 2006-07. Rewari-Jhajjar-Rohtak railway line made constructed and provide infrastructure facilities to industry at large. Survey for Loharu-Bhiwani railway line also ordered. Metro connection to Delhi to Bahadurgarh is work in progress.

Table 3: Railway Over Bridges (ROBs) identified in Master Plan in Haryana

Description	Nos.
ROBs completed and opened to traffic	3
ROBs under construction	21
ROB likely to be taken up	19

Source: PHD Research Bureau, Haryana: State Profile

Table 3 shows progress of railway over bridges in Haryana. Haryana has successfully completed 3 Railway Over Bridges and 21 ROBs are under construction. Haryana government has plans to construct another 19 ROBs to boost the railway transportation in Haryana.

Bridge and Flyover

Bridge plays an important role in interrupted connectivity to transportation. Government of Haryana plan to construct 63 new rails over bridges in state for interrupted connectivity to transportation.

Road

Highly developed roads boost the economy growth of state. Construction work has started for 135 kilometers long Kundli-Manesar-Palwal Expressway to connect National Highway No.1, 2, 8. Construction of 407 kilometers long new roads and improvement of 3,540 kilometers roads completed at a cost of Rs. 449.14 crore. Work has been started for four-laning of Delhi-Rohtak Highway (NH-10), Zirakpur-Ambala National Highway, Zirakpur-Kalka Highway and Gurgaon-Faridabad Road. 6/8 laning of Gurgaon-Delhi Highway (NH-8) at a cost of about Rs. 775 crore is work in progress. Work started for elevated Highway at Badarpur and Panipat for decongesting traffic.

Table 4: Road infrastructures in Haryana

Category of road	Length in KMs
National Highway	1957
State Highway	2128
Major District roads	1425
Other District roads	20315
Total	25825

Source: PHD Research Bureau, Haryana: State Profile

Table 4 shows progress of road infrastructures in Haryana. Haryana share 1957 km long national highway which connected Haryana to other state. Haryana has also constructed 2128 km long state highway which connect the districts at large. Haryana have long Major district

and other district roads. Haryana constantly try to develop its road infrastructure for Industry progress and economic growth.

Water

Water is need of every individual and industry. Drinking water supply augmented in 634 villages, colonies of Scheduled Castes in 421 villages and 22 towns. Works in progress to augment drinking water supply in 503 villages of Mewat area at a cost of Rs. 206 crore. 207 tube wells and five boosting stations installed.

Power

Power is play paramount role in industry development and growth of economy. Enterprising plan to bridge demand and supply gap of power. Different projects to generate 5,665 MW of power launched and MoU signed. 17 new sub-stations and 6,500 new transformers installed to improve the distribution system. Work initiated for 1065 MW gas-based plant and 1000 MW coal-based plant at Faridabad. Construction in progress at 600 MW coal-based plant at Yamunanagar. Proposal sent to Government of India to build a 4x700 Nuclear Power Plant at Fatehabad. Haryana government planning to generate additional 1,400 Mega Watt electricity through non-conventional sources.

Figure 2: Total Installed Power Capacity in Haryana

Source: PHD Research Bureau, Haryana: State Profile

Figure 2 shows the progress of Haryana on the basis of total installed power capacity. Haryana has independent in power supply and also supply the power other states. In year 2005-06 total installed power capacity in Haryana was 4000 MV and in year 2014-15 it

increased from 4000 to 12000. Industry can enjoy the full power capacity of Haryana for industry development.

Buses

New fleet of luxury 'Volvo' buses introduced and 450 buses of Haryana Roadways replaced.

Employment

Table 5: Employment Scenario

Employment	Number
Total No. of Employment Exchanges (December 2012)	56
Employment in Public Sector/PSUs (2012-13)	375106
Employment in Private Organized Sector	394767
Total Employment (2012-13)	769873
No. of Haryana Govt. Employees (March, 2012)	335945

Source: PHD Research Bureau, Haryana: State Profile

Table 5 shows the employment scenario in Haryana. Haryana have 56 employment exchanges. Total number of 375106 people engaged in public sector units and 394767 people in private organizations. Haryana government provides 335945 jobs to people.

SEZ Garhi Harsaru

As a sequel to the new Industrial Policy announced by the Govt. of Haryana. Govt. of India has approved in principle the setting up of a Special Economic Zone (SEZ) near Garhi Harsaru in District Gurgaon. The SEZ is being set up in two phases over an area of 3000 acre at an estimated cost of Rs.2060 crore. The SEZ, which is being set up by HSIIDC would help in accelerating growth-led development besides promoting Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and resultant exports. The scheme was introduced in the Exim Policy 2000 with a view to provide hassle free environment for export production. The focus of SEZ is to remove restrictive export-import regulations, ensure trade liberalization, simplify procedures relating to administration of foreign trade and provide incentives to certain export categories to generate exports from the country.

The proposed SEZ will be a duty free enclave and a deemed foreign territory where no license would be required for imports. The import of capital goods, raw materials,

consumables etc. and their procurement from the domestic market will be exempted from customs duty and central excise. The supplies from Domestic Tariff Area (DTA) to SEZ units will be treated as deemed exports. 100% FDI in manufacturing sector will be allowed through automatic route for the projects being set up in SEZ and the profits earned by these units will be allowed to be repatriated freely without any dividend balancing requirement. In addition to above the goods imported or procured locally without the payment of duty shall be utilized over the approval period of 5 years. The SEZ units will be provided in-house custom clearance and no separate documentation would be required for custom and Exim Policy.

The proposed site is on the State Highway leading from Gurgaon to Pataudi abutting the Delhi-Jaipur National Highway. The SEZ has been planned to cater to a wide spectrum of target segment such as; automobiles and auto components, high precision industries, textiles and readymade garments, pharmaceuticals, IT industry, white goods and light engineering goods. The project has been conceived to be developed as an integrated self-contained industrial township with a flyover on NH 8 to provide free flow of traffic. Industry related infrastructure of truly international standard shall be provided in the form of wide roads, dedicated electrification, water supply, storm water drainage, common effluent treatment plant etc.

1715 acres of land for the first phase of this project is in an advanced stage of acquisition and the process to acquire the land for the second phase is being initiated shortly. About 2400 units would be set up in this township providing direct employment to more 60,000 workers. When implemented, these units are expected to generate export earnings to the tune of Rs.42000 crore.

Reliance Haryana SEZ - Country's the largest SEZ

Reliance has incorporated a company by the name of Reliance Haryana SEZ to set up this multi-product zone. The 25,000-acre SEZ is tipped to be India's largest. Apart from basic industries, the project will attract next-generation businesses like biotechnology. Of the total area of the SEZ, 6,500 acres have been earmarked for low-polluting industries, 5,000 acres each for basic infrastructure and commercial establishments, 3,750 acres for residential purposes and 1,250 acres each for institutional area, leisure and entertainment.

The idea is to develop the critical mass. Development of infrastructure is a continuous process but considering that the project would be developed over an area of 25,000 acres, the investment could anywhere be between Rs 25,000-40,000 crore. The competition of this SEZ will not be with the SEZs of other states. We would be competing with the most favoured investment destinations such as Singapore, Malaysia, Dubai and China.”

The SEZ by Reliance would be in addition to nine SEZs already approved in principle by the Central Government in Haryana. The areas that could be successfully developed in this SEZ are automobiles, auto components, agro based industry, biotech, IT and garments, strive to get the best of the Fortune 500 companies to invest.

KMPE

Development of the Global Corridor: Kundli-Manesar-Palwal (KMP) Western Expressway
For the development of world-class infrastructure in the state, Government of Haryana has plan to develop the Global Corridor along Kundli-Manesar-Palwal (KMP) Western Expressway. In this corridor, top class infrastructure facilities that will be at par with international standards are being created. These are meant to meet not only the needs and dreams of the investors but also those who will be living there. Further, there will be a number of specialized economic activities in this corridor, making it growth centric. Each lead economic activity is envisaged to be the focus of a self sustaining specialized and independent cluster city. A number of such cluster cities integrated under one umbrella will provide the overall spatial form of the global urban corridor. In between these nodes, recreational, forest and green area will be developed.

The Expressway will enable strong linkages between the industrial units in the SEZ and the industrial concentrations, within the Haryana Sub-Region of National Capital Region. The Express highway linking the National Highway NO.1, 10, and 8 by passing the National Capital Territory Delhi has been proposed for spatial integration. The project has been envisaged for better coordination and administrative convenience. These industrial concentrations are given as under:

- Panipat-Sonipat_kundli Industrial Corridor on National Highway No.1.
- Bhadurgarh-Rohatak Industrial Corridor on National Highway No.10.
- Gurgaon-Manesar-Bawal Industrial Corridor on National Highway No.8.
- Faridabad-Palwal Industrial Corridor on National Highway No.1-A.

CONCLUSION

Infrastructure development basically dependent on investment made provided by government and private bodies. For infrastructure development mutually coordination between government and private bodies is necessary. This is responsibility of state and centre government to provide enough budgets in state to development of state. We know that industry can be attract by the development of good infrastructure facilities. So, development of infrastructure facilities should be on high priorities of state and central government. It is confirm with study that a state can only attract the industry by the good infrastructure facilities. Developments of infrastructure not only attract the capital within country but also from the foreign countries. It is concluded from the study government should boost the infrastructure facilities for economic and social growth. Government can go through PPP model to boost the infrastructure facilities. It is concluded from the study that share of Haryana in india's total investment is not remarkable and government should focus on increase the investment share. State government from time to time should organize investment summit to attract investment from foreign and country part.

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